

Women Domestic Workers - A Appraisal

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OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: May

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2321-788X

Impact Factor: 3.025

DOI:

[https://doi.org/10.5281/
zenodo.3335919](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3335919)

The International Labour Organisation (ILO) defines “Domestic work” as more households or for one or work performed in. “Domestic workers” are defined as all people engaged in local work within an employment relationship. This determination allows us to capture the great variety within this group: a domestic worker may work part-time or full-time, live in the house of the employer (live-in) or have her or his place of residence (live-out). Domestic workers can be selected via private or recruitment agencies employment or directly. It is not unfrequent even to carried out this variety of work within one’s own family. Domestic workers may do several different tasks, from cleaning, cooking, and washing to gardening or driving for the family. Many works with people who need care, such as children, persons who are sick, elderly, or with a disability. In various countries, domestic workers are called in different ways, such as helpers, servants, or maids, but these derogatory and condescending terms lose to acknowledge their efforts as original workers.

According to the International Labour Organisation, currently there are at least 67.1 million, worldwide, adult domestic workers, but this number is likely to be much more significant due to high familiarity and privilege in the sector, as well as lack of specific statistics based on criteria and univocal definitions. Most domestic workers concentrate in Latin America and Asia, but the situation is different when we recognize only those of migrant background as half of them work in North America and Europe. The International Labour Organisation defines “domestic work” as for one or more households or work performed. “Domestic workers” are defined as whole people engaged in local work within an employment connection. This definition allows us to capture the great variety within this group: A domestic worker may work part-time or full-time, live in the house of the employer (live-in) or have her or his place of residence. Local workers can be hired via private employment or directly or recruitment agencies. It is not unordered even to carry out this kind of work within one’s own family. Domestic workers may do several different tasks, from cleaning, cooking, and washing to gardening or driving for the family. Many works with people who need care,

such as sick, persons who are elderly, children, or with a disability. In different nations, domestic workers are called in different ways, such as servants, maids or helpers, but these unfavorable and condescending terms lose to acknowledge their efforts as real workers.

- A domestic worker is a person who is employed in any household on a temporary or permanent basis to do the household work.
- In the decade after liberalization, there was a nearly 120% increase in the number of domestic workers in India.
- Women constitute over two-thirds of the workforce in this unorganized sector.
- According to estimates by the International Labour Organisation, there are at least four million domestic servants in India.
- Domestic work as a employs too many to remain unregulated and financial activity is too vast. Though the 2011 NSSO data placed the number of domestic workers at 3.9 million, trade unions estimate the amount to be around 10 million.
- Most of these are from vulnerable associations – landless OBCs or Adivasis, Dalits. Nearly all of them are migrant workers. And an overwhelming number are women.

According to the ILO, presently there are at least 67.1 million adult domestic workers global, but this estimate is likely to be much higher due to huge informality and irregularity in the sector, as well as lack of specific statistics based on criteria and univocal definitions. Most domestic workers concentrate in Latin America and Asia, but the position is different when we analyze only those of migrant background as half of them work in Europe and North America.

Today the demand for care work is rapidly increasing and pays domestic. Three significant trends, with varying regional differences, have been associated with growth in domestic work:

- synthesis of women in the labor market: The increase in women's employment, a passage from single to double wage-earning families;
- changes in people trends: lower fertility rates, increasing life expectancy, and rapid population aging;
- changes to economic and welfare policies: neo-liberal macro-economic policies are tightening social policy budgets, delegating them from the government to families and weakening public care services.

Domestic labor, particularly the local women work, is not an officially recognized one in India. These women are generally illiterate and have very less awareness of their rights. Other social issues like child labor, human trafficking, and such are given extensive coverage by the media, whereas the domestic women are neglected. It is normal to see women folk working in as housekeepers in every town and cities. But because of lack of knowledge and literacy, they are the most unorganized and highly exploited one. There are many factors which are responsible for the increase in the number of these women domestic workers. Here in this paper, an attempt is executed to study the problems of the local workers, particularly the women domestic workers.

Causes for the increase in domestic labor: Normally, there are many causes for the rise in the demand for the women workers. The present modern world due to the modernization and other factors it is essential for both the husband and wife to work. Particularly in the metropolis, the high cost of living has made it inevitable to do so. Along with this the increasing number of nuclear families where there is no space for the members other than the family, i.e., husband, wife and the children, it is inevitable for them to hire a worker for their domestic works. In many families, the elder people/patients who are suffering from long term disseses needs the help and support of the local workers in the form of nurses/ caretakers. The reduced involvement of the parents in the extended family In caring for children has also contributed to this cause. Increasing the numbers of such cases, the demand for domestic workers also increased.

Along with these major causes, there are many other causes which have contributed to this increasing demand for domestic women workers. As the number has increased, the problems also increased. It is approximately that nearly 20 million domestic workers are there in India, including women, children, and men out of which almost 90% are women. It is approximately that nearly Four Lakhs women domestic workers are there in Bangalore Metropolises alone. Most of these domestic workers are from weaker sections of the societies belonging to the low touchable communities.

Problems of Women Domestic Workers

According to the International Domestic Workers' Federation, some face multiple forms of violence: physical abuse, intimidation, threats, bullying, sexual assault, harassment, being provided poor-quality food and a lack of privacy. Severe instances of violence, including murder, have been documented. Low wages, physical and sexual abuse, exploitation, more work-less salary, Ill-treatment. Like in any other sectors, the workers of this domestic labor are also struggling hard with many problems

Current Position of Domestic Servants

- Most of these are from vulnerable associations – Dalits, Adivasis, or landless OBCs.
- Most of them are an overwhelming number are women and migrant workers.
- Many resorts to domestic work because of the decline of employment opportunities in the manufacturing sectors and agriculture.
- The work has no reputation and commonly considered as a menial work in exchange for some amount.

Domestic Workers can be Classified Into Five Major Groups

- Full time/Live-in domestic workers
- Part-time / Live-out domestic worker
- Internal (within the state) Migrant Domestic Workers
- Inter-state domestic workers (with In India)
- Overseas domestic workers

Nature of Full time/Live-in domestic workers: Live-in domestic workers reside at the place of employment. They are engaged in all household work ranging from housekeeping, washing clothes, utensils, cooking, and even involved in children, baby or elderly care. They depend on their employers for basic requirements such as shelter and food. Most full-time domestic workers are women who have migrated or have been trafficked from villages to cities in the research of employment. They are, unmarried, to a large extent, children, and sometimes married young girls, widowed women or separated.

Part-time/Live out domestic workers: Half-time domestic workers are commonly locals or migrants in the city where they are employed. They mostly live in slums and work in the houses of many employers to earn their livelihood. All are called part-timers not because they do only part-time work but because they appear not to stay with the employer and are not required to be on call 24 hours a day. They either work every day for one employer or repeatedly perform specific tasks like cooking, dishes, washing clothes, or for several employers. Part-timers are few dependent on their employers than full-time workers. They live, including their families and run their houses, as well as those of their employers. However, they are few dependent on their employers for their basic requirements and are characterized by a higher degree of independence than the live-in domestic workers.

Internal (within the state) Migrant Domestic Workers: Many women migrate from their villages to work as domestic workers.

This migration takes two forms:

- Overseas Domestic Workers
- Inter-state Domestic Workers

Overseas Domestic Workers:- Whether the domestic worker remains in India or travels to Southeast Asia or the Middle East, she finds herself in a different environment, away from her family and adjusting to food, cultures and new languages. Migrants continue typically live-in domestic workers and are thus common vulnerable to sexual abuse and physical, deprivation and excessively long working hours. Many of them are from tribular regions, and as live-in domestic workers are compounded by their ethnicity and the traditional difference they face as women. Despite these problems, poor women are required to migrate to cities and foreign countries to supplement their families' small incomes.

Migration within India: Migration from rural areas to mature cities typically transpires due to debt bondage, poverty, sudden death in the family, country, and male unemployment. The beauty of city life acts as a further "pull" factor inducing women to migrate and young girls. Working in cities is seen as a solution to poverty, and villagers are unaware of the exploitative working conditions and poor reward that the vast majority of domestic workers have to survive. Additionally, a large number of domestic workers arrive from areas, which have been subjected to natural disasters and human-made crises and as such are from displaced societies. Increasingly, "trafficking agencies" have become a significant factor in encouraging internal migration. In the arena of domestic work, organized trafficking is getting a place as villagers living in the cities are come back to their native homes to bring more women, girls, and children into this labor sector. Once the girls arrive in the towns, their wages are typically locked, or they go unpaid to pay the traffickers a fee for securing employment.

Migration outside of India: There is a grown demand from wealthier industrialized countries for menial, cheap and domestic labor. Migrants from more poor, less developed countries such as India can jump to this possibility as it does not require any high skills or education. Thousands of Indian women travel to countries in South East Asia, the Middle East, and North America and sometimes Europe in search of jobs paying higher wages. However, these women earn the cheapest salary for an international worker, even though they may be making more than they would in India for the same job. Many women move abroad to send money back home to improve their quality of life in India. However, in traveling abroad, they become unsafe to corrupt recruitment practices, withheld salaries, lack of work contracts, sexual, physical, and emotional abuse at the workplace and in many cases, their travel documents are withheld, and they are prevented from coming back to home. In India, the procedure for transferring abroad for work is not controlled. The Indian government has not executed a pre-migration program aimed at educating migrants of their rights. To travel overseas, migrants are required to borrow vast sums of cash, often with exorbitant interest rates, to pay fees to agents.

In many cases, the migrants, who are often uneducated and naïve to the potential risks of entrusting huge sums of money with foreigners, are the victims of scams of the fly-by-night agents. These con artists do not secure the contracted job abroad, give them false tickets, or do not achieve the relevant paperwork so that the women can legally work as domestic workers. Thus, many women search themselves in a foreign country without the required papers. They are especially unsafe to not being paid the promised salary and being held in conditions of slavery without the knowledge to complain to the police. In many cases, the employer holds on to the domestic worker's passport, preventing her from contacting the Indian embassy to file complaints or leaving.

Issues

- Most of the domestic servants are women, migrants many are minors and belong to the lowest end of the financial spectrum. This makes them easy to replace, and easier still to exploit.
- Indeed, hardly a week goes by without some news statement about domestic help being abused by her employer. Cases of torture, sexual assault, beatings, and incarceration are common.
- Since they belong to the unorganized sector, no laws are safeguarding their rights – no minimum wage obligations, no health or insurance benefits, and no job safety whatsoever.
- The nexus of the state and the market has managed to keep domestic work outside the realm of economic regulation.
- Neither the Maternity Benefits Act nor the Minimum Wages Act or any of the scores of other labor laws applies to domestic work.
- Domestic workers can be hired and fired at will. The employer has no legally binding obligations.
- In a country where 93% of the workforce is in the unorganized sector and therefore beyond the purview of most labor laws, domestic workers represent a new low in terms of disempowerment: they are not even recognized as workers. Their work — cooking, cleaning, dish-washing, baby-sitting — is not recognized as work by the state.
- Apart from facing routine, structural exploitation in the form of low wages, heavy workloads, and long hours, domestic workers face graver dangers, as is evident from cases of employers confining and assaulting them coming to light with frightening regularity.
- The inequality of domestic workers' circumstances is accentuated by the fact their workplace falls within the privacy of the homes of people that are invariably more privileged than they are.
- Although successive governments have drafted policies, they are yet to become law.

Concerns Associated with Domestic Workers in India

- There are around 3.9 million domestic workers in India, according to 2011 NSSO data. However, according to trade unions estimate, there are approximately 10 million domestic workers in India. Most of these are from vulnerable communities – Adivasis, Dalits, or landless OBCs. Nearly all of them are migrant workers. And an overwhelming number are women. But there exists not one law that deals explicitly with this unorganized sector, of which women constitute over two-thirds of the workforce in this unorganized sector.
- Neither the Maternity Benefits Act nor the Minimum Wages Act or any of the scores of other labor laws applies to domestic work. Domestic workers can be hired and fired at will. The employer has no legally binding obligations.
- Most of the local workers are bare of legal working age and their wages less than the minimum fixed by the government.
- Only a few states like Rajasthan, Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala, and Bihar have fixed minimum wages, but in most cases, the wage rate is fixed arbitrarily, is too low and irrelevant to those working in urban areas where the cost of living is much higher.
- In a country where 93% of the workforce is in the unorganized sector and therefore beyond the purview of most labor laws, domestic workers represent a new low in terms of disempowerment: they are not even recognized as workers. Their work — cooking, cleaning, dish-washing, baby-sitting — is not recognized as work by the state. (Lack of recognition)

- Their employers range from India's elite to its nouveau riche, many of whom still believe in the traditional divide between servants and masters. Abuse, mental, physical, or sexual, of these women, is not uncommon.
- Cases of torture, beatings, sexual assault, and incarceration are common. Indeed, hardly a week goes by without some news report about domestic help being abused by her employer.

Challenges

- Their work — cooking, cleaning, dish-washing, baby-sitting — is not recognized as work by the state.
- Domestic work as an economic activity is too vast and employs too many to remain unregulated.
- Neither the Maternity Benefits Act nor the Minimum Wages Act or any other labor laws applies to domestic work.
- Domestic workers can be hired and fired at will. The employer has no legally binding obligations.
- Organizing domestic workers has been a massive challenge as the workplace is inaccessible and multiple.
- As a result, the demand for better wages or working conditions through an organized association has been ineffective.
- India is a signatory to the ILO's 189th convention, known as the Convention on Domestic Workers; but has not ratified it yet.
- Little progress has been made in passing Domestic Workers Welfare and Social Security Act, 2010' Bill.

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